

BEING SUCCESSFUL ON ASSIGNMENTS IN TEACHING LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article is about how to be successful. People have several different reasons to learn a foreign language; people often learn a language for practical reasons while others have a particular love for the language and its people. Language teachers are often very aware of the career benefits that language proficiency can offer, but learning the language is just an abstract undertaking needed for an academic degree to many language learners. If a teacher adopts the same method for all students, then some students will not be able to learn anything. In order to keep students interested in learning, students must be motivated by the teacher.

Key words: Motivation, language learning and teaching, homework, assessment, success and failure.

It is no doubt that motivation is an important factor for success in learning. It is the combination of two factors: Learning purpose and attitude; if knowledge is important for the learner, learning occurs without any need to learn it. Teachers are concerned about developing a particular kind of motivation in their students - the motivation to learn. Many elements make up the motivation to learn. Planning, concentration on the goal, metacognitive awareness of what you intend to learn and how you intend to learn it, the active search for new information, clear perception of feedback, pride and satisfaction in achievement, and no anxiety or fear of failure. Thus, motivation to learn involves more than wanting or intending to learn. It includes the quality of the student's mental efforts. The biggest issue of the class today is that the teacher has no understanding of effective teaching and motivation. Teachers assume that their students are empty buckets to be filled with knowledge. However, students have total personalities and teachers must understand effective teaching and students' features, otherwise, they will not be successful in teaching. First, the student is a dynamic, living, growing, developing and maturing personality. The teacher is not directly concerned with the hereditary factors in the student. By the time the student starts school, he already has a well-developed personality. This means that he/she is organized while it is the individual that has to be satisfied with any need and want. Second, students are also motivated by unconscious and semiconscious needs and wants. Fortunately, many of these can be redirected by proper

motivation in formal education. School programs must consider the dynamic nature of the student, his/her experience, his total environment and individual differences. Experience is the best teacher in learning. There cannot be learning without experience, and every experience can be an education. The quality of the education is determined by the quality of experience on the part of the learner. Experiences are also important for learning. We interpret new experience in the light of the old. Learning is based on past experience and when tied with “the total pattern” it becomes more effective in comprehension and speed of learning. Assignments also help in the practice; it is like doing the try outs to discover new outcomes. This practice also helps the students to prepare for exams and Seven 67 similar unseen problems that might come handy. Therefore, it is not restricted to assignments; the students are required to write a good assignment. Success and failure are human-built and subjective concepts that are changeable to the point of being retroactively altered due to a change in perception. An analysis shows that success and failure are created by humans and are defined by human experience, emotions, decisions and judgment. The “human” element, when it comes to the definition of success and failure, is the reason why success and failure do not have standard parameters or set rules that apply to all people and all circumstances n school, learning success and failure can be useful within limitations. The success-failure motive runs all through life and it is the chief determiner of morale. Every effort is conditioned by trial and error or trial and success. It is determined in the mind of the learner. Success and failure should be balanced so that the student does not lose his perspective. In the classroom, the teacher can manipulate the situation so that every child will get a taste of success to temper the ill effects of failure. Experimental studies show that learning with positive guidance is superior to negative guidance. The positive is related to failure. All these suggestions may or should create motivation in the classroom. If a student has the desire to learn, it may imply at some point in time that the student is receptive to learning. A student may be motivated to learn by an idea, emotion or physical need. If a student does not want to learn, it is unlikely that learning will occur. Sometimes physical motives may stimulate a person or student to learn. Student’s beliefs and behaviours might be major target of teaching and at the same time, they affect the probability that change will occur. It is common sense that motivation is largely a product of learners’ learning experiences. Learner’s belief can be powerful motivators and they may be influenced by families and teachers. A student should believe that whoever studies hard can succeed. However, motivation may be the only key to obtain good

grades and to prevent failure. In this work we made different definitions appear generally to have three common dominators that may be said to characterize the phenomenon of motivation.

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